

Flexural Performance of Cross-Laminated Pultruded Hollow Section GFRPs Beam

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Abstract

Pultruded GFRP has an excellent strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and simplicity of manufacture, making it an appealing material for civil engineering, architecture, and landscape architecture projects. This research paper presents experimental investigations and theoretical analyses on the flexural performance of Cross-Laminated Pultruded Hollow Section GFRPs (CL-GFRPs)—the initial stage of the research involved material characterization tests to elucidate the mechanical properties of the GFRP. Subsequently, four-point bending tests were conducted on four beams. The study compares beams strengthened with carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP BT70-20) to unstrengthened control beams, analyzing the effect of different fiber orientations on the bending properties. Four CL-GFRPs were utilized, each comprising GFRP Type square five (rectangle) with dimensions of 1450 mm long, 200 mm wide, and 60 mm thickness, arranged in two layers. The outcomes of the four-point bending tests revealed that the load capacity of BTUG was higher than that of BTBG beams. Incorporating CFRP into the transversal arrangement of the beam's CL-GFRPs enhanced the bending performance, strength, and stiffness, contributing significantly to civil and architectural applications.

Keywords: Cross-lamination, hollow beam, pultruded GFRP, CFRP, bending test

1. Introduction

By offering a cooperative platform for discussing shell and spatial structure concepts, analysis, design, and construction, hopes to value conventional and novel ideas equally and ultimately aid in developing a low-carbon civilization. One of the novel ideas that developed in civilization is the utilization of GFRP. According to ACMA et al. [1], Ali et al. [2], and Chen et al. [3], the transition from traditional materials to composites in architectural building and construction applications has occurred at varying rates, depending on individual use. FRP composites were used to create complex facades, curved curves, and other distinctive architectural characteristics, overcoming typical material restrictions. As the architectural community becomes more aware of composites' benefits and design freedom, the production of these composites for buildings is likely to increase dramatically. Compared to traditional wood, concrete, masonry, or metallic materials, composites in external siding and cladding applications improve durability and reduce dead and seismic loads. Zhang et al. [4], Liu et al. [5], and Bank [6] state that the requirement for sustainable and long-lasting building materials has prompted the development of novel solutions, such as the mix of pultruded GFRP profiles with standard concrete

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components. Pultruded GFRP has a good strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and simplicity of manufacture, making it an appealing material for civil engineering projects. Bank [7] states that the FRP systems should not be utilized to strengthen the compression area of flexural components. If FRP reinforcing systems are put in the compression zones of flexural components, they should not be considered to bear any compression stress, and they should be suitably connected to avoid local buckling, which might lead to premature failure. According to Li et al.[8], there are several forms of FRP composites, including Carbon FRP (CFRP), Glass FRP (GFRP), and Basalt FRP (BFRP). CFRP provides superior mechanical qualities and fatigue, creep, and corrosion resistance. However, it is pricey, which limits its use in some technical applications. In turn, Li et al.[9] state that the most often utilized FRP rods in engineering are CFRP and GFRP. Carbon/glass fiber reinforced polymer hybrid composite (HFRP) rods offer a cost-effective and high-performance alternative to CFRP rods due to GFRP's cheap cost, tensile strength, and deformability.

Scholars have also investigated fiber-reinforced pultruded profile sandwich composites that reveal weak transverse bearing capacity, Alhawamdeh et al. [13]. To address the weaknesses of the hollow pultrude profile, especially for transversal arrangement, this study proposed a new design by a combination of transversal and longitudinal pultrude profiles by cross laminated-pultruded hollow section GFRPs (CL-GFRPs). The surface of the transverse pultrude profile will be strengthened with CFRP to avoid failure and local buckling. Through four-point bending tests and theoretical analysis, the flexural behavior of CL-GFRPs is investigated based on varying orientations and positions of the GFRP beam and comparing the performance of unstrengthened control beams with strengthened beams. The performance of the beams is then analyzed in terms of load-deflection curves and mode of failure. At the end of this paper, theoretical models are proposed to predict the beam's elastic deflection and load-carrying capacity.

2. Experimental program

2.1 General Description

Section GFRPs (CL-GFRPs) made from GFRP with a density of $1,791\text{kg/m}^3$. Each CL-GRP beam is 1450 mm long, 200 mm wide, and 60 mm thick, with two layers. The CL-GFRPs will be reinforced using carbon fiber BT70-20—the position of CFRP based on the result of the bending test from control beams. E2500 epoxy resins is employed for the impregnation of the specimens. The length of CFRP is 100 mm, with three layers. The number of CFRP layers is chosen as an experimental parameter only. Two kinds of beams were tested. Two unstrengthened beams are called control beam transversal bottom GFRP (CBTBG), and control beam transversal upper GFRP (CBTUG). Furthermore, two strengthened beams are called strengthened beam transversal bottom GFRP (SBTBG) and strengthened beam transversal upper GFRP (SBTUG). Detailed specifications of the specimen's configuration are provided in Table 1.

2.2 Materials

Three material properties were tested: compressive, tensile, and shear. The Universal testing machine manufactured by Maekawa was used to test the material properties. Four types of compressive tests were conducted. Two of these tests involved specimens that adapt to the specimen's condition (box and double channel). Two beams were designed based on the direction of the fibers, namely longitudinal and transversal (JISK7018) [11]. Tensile tests were conducted in longitudinal and transversal directions (JISK7164) [12] per the fiber direction. Shear tests were performed using the V-notched rail shear method (ASTM-D7078) [13]. Material properties test results can be seen in Table 2. CFRP properties are in Table 3, and epoxy resin properties are in Table 4.

Table 1: List of specimens for CL-GFRP beams

Name of Specimens	Volume	Cross section beams	Explanations	Specimen dimension ($h \times w \times l$) (mm)
CBTUG	1		Bending Test for CL GFRP beam without strengthening, Epoxy Resin E2500	60x200x1450
SBTUG	1		Bending Test for CL GFRP beam with bottom strengthening, Epoxy Resin E2500, CFRP BT70-20	60x200x1450
CBTBG	1		Bending Test for CL GFRP beam without strengthening Epoxy Resin, E2500	60x200x1450
SBTBG	1		Bending Test for CL GFRP beam with upper strengthening, Epoxy Resin E2500, CFRP BT70-20	60x200x1450

CBTUG = Control Beam Transversal Upper GFRP
SBTUG = Strengthened Beam Transversal Upper GFRP
CBTBG = Control Beam Transversal Bottom GFRP
SBTBG = Strengthened Beam Transversal Bottom GFRP

Table 2: Material properties of GFRP

Material Properties	Symbol	Value	unit
Density	ρ	1,791	kg/m ³
Young's modulus in longitudinal direction	E_L	27,46	GPa
Young's modulus in transversal direction	E_T	8,88	GPa
Young's modulus in transversal direction (BC)	E_{TBC}	28,80	GPa
Young's modulus in transversal direction (CC)	E_{TCC}	8,24	GPa
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0,245	
Shear Modulus	G	3,42	GPa
Longitudinal tensile strength	σ_{LT}	462,56	MPa
Longitudinal compressive strength	σ_{LC}	276,58	MPa
Transverse tensile strength	σ_{TT}	40,69	MPa
Transverse compressive strength	σ_{TC}	81,60	MPa
Transverse compressive strength (BC)	σ_{TBC}	35,29	MPa
Transverse compressive strength (CC)	σ_{TCC}	84,99	MPa
Shear strength	τ	61,84	MPa

Table 3: Characteristics of carbon fiber [14]

Type	Fiber direction	Sheet Thickness (mm)	Fiber Weight (gr/m ²)	Density (gr/cm ³)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (GPa)
BT70-20	0°	0.056	100	1.8	230	2.9
	90°	0.056	100	1.8	230	2.9

Table 4: Material Properties Epoxy Resin [15]

Epoxy Resin	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile shear bond strength (MPa)
E2500	4.1	0.37	30	12.5

2.3 Specimens preparation process

GFRP was manufactured using Pultrusion, an automated, continuous technique that manufactures FRP components from raw materials. An automated method for creating continuous, stable, cross-section composite structures that is economical is pultrusion. Common-sized various pultruders commonly manufacture I, H, and tubular profile shapes, Bank [16]. The specimens of CL-GFRP beams were manufactured at the experiment Laboratory of Toyohashi University of Technology. The manufacturing process involves several stages, in the following sequence: preparation of specimens, cutting specimens for transversal layer, and at the same time, a mixture of epoxy resin is prepared with a ratio of 2:1 (base resin: curing agent), according to the manufacturer instruction. All the CL-GFRPs beams were molded via hand layup process. The manufacturing of specimens process is depicted in Figure 1 (a), (b), (c), and (d).

Figure 1: Manufactures specimens process (a) GFRP (b) apply epoxy resin to GFRP (c) apply epoxy resin between CFRP and CL-GFRPs beams (d) curing specimens

2.4 Test setup and instrumentation

All previously prepared beams are subjected to failure tests using a compression testing machine with a maximum loading capacity of 2,000 kN. A four-point bending test scheme is applied to all beams. The clear span of the beam is 1,200 mm, equivalent to 20 times the height of the beam. The distance between two load points is set at 400 mm. During the testing process, the applied load is measured through a load cell embedded within the testing machine, while the vertical displacement (δ) that occurs is captured through measurements using five displacement transducers mounted along the bottom face of the beam.

Furthermore, nine longitudinal strain gauges are utilized to record the strain profile distribution along the cross-sectional height of the beam at mid-span. In comparison, two diagonal strain gauges are positioned between the support and load points. Additional rubber pads are installed at the bottom of

the loading points and the top of the supports to prevent local failure. A detailed diagram of the beam test is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Detail diagram test setup actual view

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Load-deflection curve

Figure 3 depicts the load-deflection curve at the mid-span ($\delta -3$) based on the position GFRP. The load-displacement curves of specimens in Figure 3 (a) further illustrate the ultimate capacities of CBTUG (18,39 kN) and CBTBG (23,35 kN). Consequently, CBTUG demonstrated a 21.26% higher load capacity than CBTBG. Similarly, Figure 3 (b) presents the ultimate capacities of SBTUG (30,15 kN) and SBTBG (24 kN). It is shown that SBTUG is 20,40% higher than SBTBG. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the specimens BTUG exhibit superior performance capacity compared to the specimens BTBG.

The load-displacement curves between unstrengthened and strengthened beams presented in Figure 4 (a) and (b) demonstrate that strengthened beams reinforced with carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) layers exhibit an approximately 20% increase in ultimate load capacity compared to unstrengthened beams. This enhancement in ultimate bearing capacity has been validated for CL-GFRP beams reinforced with CFRP layers. From the graphs, the initial stiffness of CBTUG was higher than CBTBG, and SBTUG was higher than SBTBG. This indicated that the position of GFRP would influence the stiffness of the beams. The BTUG position is better than that of BTBG. The strengthened beams show an increase in stiffness. This proves that CFRP layers improved the stiffness of beams.

Figure 4 also compares experimental and predicted load-displacement graphs for CL-GFRP beams. The theoretical ($\delta_{m.anal}$) and experimental deflections ($\delta_{m.exp}$) were measured from the linear elastic zone at a steady stage load. The theoretical deflection ($\delta_{m.anal}$) was calculated using Eq. (1), and the experimental deflections ($\delta_{m.exp}$) were calculated from the mid-span of the specimens using a dial indicator. The predicted curves matched the experimental curve only at the first slope. With the applied load increasing to failure, there was a significant discrepancy between the experimental and analytical response. This was due to the assumption of linear elastic behavior of the constituent materials in the analytical model, which does not match their actual responses. The theoretical value was attributed to the fact that the strength design value employed in this theory does not account for the epoxy resin effect.

The total displacement at the mid-point can be expressed as the Eq. (1)

$$\delta_m = \delta_{bending} + \delta_{shear} = \frac{P}{48EI} (3aL^2 - 4a^3) + \frac{P}{2GA_{eq}} a \quad (1)$$

where δ_m the midspan deflection, L denotes the precise span of the specimen, and a signifies the distance from the loading point to the support. The longitudinal flexural stiffness EI and the shear stiffness GA_{eq} .

Figure 3: Load-midspan deflection ($\delta -3$) based on position GFRP (BTBG vs BTUG)

Figure 4: Load-midspan deflection ($\delta -3$) based on unstrengthened and strengthened beams experiments and analytical (a) BTUG (b) BTBG

3.2 Failure modes

Figure 5 presents the failure modes of all tested specimens in this study. Most specimens exhibited failures at the transversal GFRP in the tension or compression area. The failure modes and load-displacement curves of the beams are coincident for each type of specimen, as evident in Figure 5.

As observed in Figures 3 and 4, the load-displacement curves of the beams for each type of specimen are coincident. The specimens BTBG exhibited linear load increase up to the first peak loads. At the same time, a popping sound was audible, and small adhesive debonding gradually occurred in the tension zone, followed by interface debonding, specifically in the middle of loading points and between loading points and support pins, as shown in Figure 5 (a). Furthermore, the strengthened

specimen shows similar failure near the support pins (Figure: 5 (c)). Subsequently, the load-displacement curves became nonlinear. The specimen continued to bear the load until the mid-span deflection reached 65 mm.

The failure process of specimen BTUG differed from that of specimen BTBG. Initially, the bearing capacity experienced a sudden decrease and subsequently increased linearly with the applied load. However, the specimen surface exhibited no macroscopic signs of failure. Upon reaching the ultimate load, a popping sound was generated, indicating the initiation of fiber fracture. The surface layer at the loading points became indented, and an initial crack was observed. The sound volume increased as the load increased further. The transversal GFRP fibers between the loading points in the compression area were crushed, and the fibers at the interface between the surface layer and the GFRP were debonded. Finally, the surface material of the specimen underwent shear deformation, followed by localized buckling, as depicted in Figures 5 : (b), while the strengthened specimen shows almost similar failure at the end of support pins, as shown in Figure 5 (d).

Figure 5: Failure modes CL-GFRP beams (a) CBTBG (b) CBTUG (c) SBTBG (d) SBTUG

4. Conclusions

Through four-point bending tests and theoretical analysis, the flexural behavior of CL-GFRPs is investigated based on varying orientations and positions of the GFRP beam and comparing the performance of unstrengthened control beams with strengthened beams. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- The result indicated that the proposed BTUG CL-GFRPs beams exhibit superior performance capacity compared to the specimens BTBG. The ultimate load capacity of BTUG is 20% higher than BTBG. Meanwhile, the strengthened beams reinforced with carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) layers exhibit an approximately 20% increase in ultimate load capacity compared to unstrengthened beams. This enhancement in ultimate bearing capacity has been validated for CL-GFRP beams reinforced with CFRP layers.

- The initial stiffness of BTUG was higher than BTBG; the difference was almost 6 %. It is indicated that the position of GFRP influences the stiffness of the beams. Meanwhile, strengthened beams show an increasing percentage of around 30,76-36,54%. This proves that CFRP layers improved the stiffness of beams.
- The failure modes of CL-GFRP beams were dominant to transversal GFRP. In this study, BTBG specimens showed adhesive debonding. In contrast, BTUG specimens experience compression failures and shear deformation followed by local buckling. The failure of the longitudinal pultrude profile was insignificant. The strengthened beam shows the same failure modes as the unstrengthened beam. However, the failures move to the surface of the pultruded profile that CFRP does not cover.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by IPB University. We acknowledge the support of the Cooperative Research Facility Center of Toyohashi University of Technology.

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